

**UNIVERSITY OF
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PMA4002 – The Essentials of Project Management

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PMA4002 The Essentials of Project Management

Introduction

This report will identify the 5 principles of project management. (1) Project Lifecycles, (2) Project Methodologies, (3) Project Governance, (4) Project Scheduling and Project Controls, (5) Project Risk Management, together with a review of the theory and application within Babcock. There are many differing lifecycles that can be used within a project, they are:

- Linear: a lifecycle that aims to complete a project within a single pass through a set of distinct phases and completed serially and span the development from the initial concept to the deployment of the ultimate output, outcome or benefits (APM, 2022).
- Iterative: a lifecycle that repeats one or more of the phases of a project or programme before proceeding to the next one with the objective of managing uncertainty of scope by allowing objectives to evolve as learning and discovering takes place (APM, 2022).
- Hybrid: a pragmatic approach to achieving beneficial change that combines a linear lifecycle for some phases or activities with an iterative lifecycle for others (APM, 2022).

Project Lifecycles

APM (2022) states that “a lifecycle is a framework comprising a series of distinct high-level stages required to transform an idea or concept into reality in an orderly and efficient manner. There are several lifecycles that can be used on a project. This report will identify the three main lifecycles that can be found being used within Babcock. They are Linear, Iterative and Hybrid lifecycles. The overall lifecycle at Babcock is the linear project lifecycle, but underneath this overarching lifecycle is much a hybrid lifecycle within the individual projects.

Figure 1: Babcock's Linear Lifecycle

Babcock is using the Linear lifecycle for a current project to meet contractual milestones on time.

Figure 2: Full Linear lifecycle (including Extended and Product Lifecycles)
(APM, 2022)

As the project develops and becomes more complex, it may be required to adopt a hybrid lifecycle as some of the work may require revisiting.

Figure 3: The hybrid lifecycle.
(APM, 2022)

Figure 4: Iterative lifecycle
(APM, 2022 and Agile Business Consortium, 2014)

Table 1: Lifecycle benefits and disadvantages

	Benefits	Disadvantages
Linear	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applies to low risk, stable projects with greater structure. • Sequential with clear outputs. • Provides a clear framework and allows maximum control and governance. • Controls and information are passed on to the next phase when predefined milestones have been reached. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requires early clarity on scope and governance. • Ascertaining if the benefits have been realised is a longer process. • Less flexible in accommodating change.
Hybrid	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flexible. • Improved risk management. • Enhanced collaboration. • Better resource utilisation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complex management. • Higher Costs. • Potential for confusion when switching methodologies. • Inconsistent processes. • Increased management effort. • Risk of scope creep.
Iterative	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Early detection of issues. • Flexible. • Improved risk management. • Better progress tracking. • Enhanced collaboration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource intensive. • Complex management. • Potential for scope creep. • Incomplete requirements. • Higher costs. • Not suitable for small projects.

Due to the complexity and scale of the projects at Babcock, a hybrid approach has been adopted to allow for change and any delay to the scope of the project. By doing so, Babcock can take advantage of opportunities for changing some processes of work to allow for the project to continue and try to remain on track. The ability to change the order of work can prevent some delay but ultimately not eliminate any risk of further delay to the project schedule.

Project Methodologies

According to Morphy (2023), "... methodology defines the work environment, whereas the method defines how the work is to be performed." There are several methodologies that can be used when managing projects. From APM, PRINCE2, Agile and Six Sigma.

APM, formed in 1972, has a structured approach which covers 4 chapters and 12 sections. APM Body of Knowledge is a foundational knowledge resource, and a pointer to other sources of information. The purpose of the APM is to reflect on current best practices and future professional needs, serving as a benchmark for change initiatives (APM, 2022).

Figure 5: APM Framework
(APM, 2023)

PRINCE2, designed in 1989, is process based and linear by design (ILX, 2017). This methodology can be tailored for many different projects that follow a waterfall lifecycle.

Figure 6: PRINCE2 methodology.
(PRINCE2, 2017)

The purpose of PRINCE2 is to be a flexible, scalable project management method using defined processes with key inputs, outputs, objectives, and activities (PRINCE2 2017). PRINCE2 has 7 principles, 7 practices and 7 themes.

Figure 7: PRINCE2 7 principles, practices and processes
(PRINCE2, 2017 / Lawton, 2023)

AGILE, developed in 2001, (PMI, 2018) is ideal if you want to get products to the market quickly and can be found more in the IT and software industry where companies release beta versions of software or games.

Figure 8: AGILE methodology.
(Hart, 2022)

AGILE is a hybrid methodology taking aspects from areas such as SCRUM, Lean and Kanban. Its purpose is to empower people, encourage accountability, and promote early benefits and continuous improvement. Agile has 4 key values and 12 operating principles (Quick, 2023).

Figure 9: AGILE 4 key values.
(Quick, 2023)

Figure 10: AGILE 12 principles.

(Quick, 2023)

Six Sigma, designed in 1987, is a data driven and customer focused. It is designed to improve the efficiency of the business and processes by reducing wasted time within projects and focuses on an existing product rather than redesigning something new.

Figure 11: Six Sigma methodology.

(Six Sigma, 2018)

Babcock follows the APM Framework and aligned to the GPMF. This framework supports the complex projects that they manage. This works well in Babcock as it allows for a hybrid approach throughout the lifecycle due to the complexity of the projects within the organisation. One of the projects is complex enough to have several mini projects within the main project and is broken down into zones. In BN06, each zone will interact independently as well as with other zones or sub projects due to the complexity of the work packages involved

Figure 12: Babcock BN06 project and zonal projects structure

(Babcock, 2023)

To enable the project's success, the choice of methodology will be based on the requirements of the project, any constraints, organisations culture, potential risks and stakeholder involvement.

Project Governance

Governance is “the framework of authority and accountability that defines and controls the outputs, outcomes and benefits from projects.” (APM, 2022)

Project governance, started in the 1990s (FRC, 2024), and became formalised in the early 2000s. Good governance will enable key decisions to be made throughout the project. Babcock adheres to legal and regulatory governance, guided by the UK Corporate Governance Code (FRC, 2024), Code of Business Conduct (Babcock, 2023), risk management, project reviews and reports, policy reviews and stakeholder engagement. Babcock conducts its governance in several ways:

1. Strategic Alignment.
2. Trust and Transparency.
3. Risk Management.
4. Operational Efficiency.
5. Long-term Sustainability.

Project Governance adds value for customers, project teams and Babcock by making the best project decisions. This is done adequately at Babcock with regular reporting periods throughout the project..

Project Scheduling and Project Control

Project scheduling is the process of organising tasks, activities, and milestones within a project to ensure it runs smoothly and is completed on time and enables tracking of those planned activities (APM, 2015). A project schedule allows for:

- A more defined scope of work and can help prevent scope creep.
- Accountability by setting activity deadlines, milestones and ownership.
- Improved alignment to ensure everybody on the project is on the same page and knows what is due to happen and when.
- Reduced risk.
- Regular reporting and use of Gantt charts can help when communicating with stakeholders.
- Better forecasting and creating a baseline can improve the accuracy of future forecasting.

Project controls are a set of tools, techniques, and processes used within a project to manage and control aspects such as time, cost, scope, quality, risk, and resources.

These processes or functions are essential for ensuring that a project is on track and can meet its final objectives (APM, 2015). Project controls allow for the monitoring of activities, decision making, risk management, cost control, and resource management.

At Babcock, the project is monitored in several ways including critical path analysis and regular baseline and schedule reviews. The critical path analysis is based on activities through the longest path of the project (APM, 2022). Due to the complexity of BN06, Babcock review the critical path regularly.

Weekly reports are produced and presented in the form of Gantt charts. These are visible to the stakeholders and to all zones within BN06. A Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) details the work that is planned to take place in each zone and shows the dependencies between zones for the project to be successful.

Figure 13: Example of a WBS
(APM, 2022)

Babcock has adopted the APM framework, though in comparison it is more a hybrid approach. This results in a complex schedule that interlinks with other zones across the project. The consequences of this are that there is often a breakdown in

communication between zones as each manage their independent schedule and resources.

Project Risk Management

Risk is ‘the potential of a situation or event to impact on the achievement of specific objectives.’ **Opportunity** is ‘a positive risk event that will have a beneficial effect on the achievement of one or more objectives’ (APM, 2022).

The risk management process involves 5 steps (1) initiate the risk, (2) identify the risk, (3) assess the risk, (4) plan responses (5) implement the risk (PRAM, 2004).

Figure 14: Babcock's Risk management process
(PRAM, 2010, Babcock, 2023)

Risk management allows you to monitor, manage and mitigate risk (Babcock, 2023). Babcock aligns risk management with the business strategic objectives and follows the ISO31000:2018 guidance and GPMF (Babcock, 2023). Actively seeking out

opportunities to counteract any potential risk to the project and allow the project to progress. Babcock use quantitative risk analysis (QRA) to predict the level of risk for the whole project. Risks are actively managed. Scope owners are held accountable for managing risk and the quality and completeness of risk information. High quality risk information and models are essential for insight and decision making. Transparency and early visibility of potential risks is encouraged.

Figure 15: Example of a QRA.
(PRAM, 2010)

Figure 16: Probability of risk diagram.
(PRAM, 2010)

Threats					Descriptor	Probability
8	15	20	23	25	Very Likely	>90%
6	10	16	21	24	Likely	>60%-90%
4	9	13	17	22	Possible	>30%-60%
2	5	11	14	19	Unlikely	>10%-30%
1	3	7	12	18	Very Unlikely	<=10%
Insignificant	Minor	Moderate	Major	Severe		
Impact / Severity						

Threats			
Very High 20-25	High 15-19	Medium 8-14	Low 1-7
Urgent attention is required to reduce exposure or Risk Owner to clearly justify otherwise.	Proactive management required to reduce exposure.	Requires monitoring and management.	Ongoing management to maintain the effectiveness of control and conduct monitoring/period reviews.

Figure 17: Risk Threat Probability Impact Diagram.

(Babcock, 2023, APM, 2023)

Probability	Descriptor	Opportunities				
>90%	Very High	25	24	22	20	14
>60%-90%	High	23	21	19	15	10
>30%-60%	Moderate	18	17	16	12	7
>10%-30%	Low	13	11	9	5	3
<=10%	Very Low	8	6	4	2	1
		Exceptional	Major	Moderate	Minor	Insignificant
Impact / Severity						

Opportunities			
High 22-25	Medium 18-21	Low 13-17	Very Low 1-12
High-priority opportunities focus on implementation subject to return on investment.	Medium-priority opportunities actively develop and implement subject to return on investment.	Low-priority opportunities develop further where practicable subject to return on investment.	Opportunities whose continued value and likelihood do not warrant pursuit.

Figure 18: Risk Opportunity Impact Diagram.
(Babcock, 2023, APM, 2023)

Any risks identified will be recorded in the risk register. This will detail the risks, who is responsible for managing the risk, what actions to be carried out to mitigate the risk or what actions have been taken toward the risk.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the essentials of project management incorporates an understanding of project lifecycles, methodologies, governance, scheduling, and risk management. Babcock's approach integrates linear, iterative, and hybrid lifecycles, and demonstrates the flexibility required to manage complex projects effectively. The use of the APM methodologies allows for a structured yet adaptable framework that supports project success. Effective project governance ensures accountability and

strategic alignment, while robust scheduling and control mechanisms facilitate timely and efficient project execution. Proactive risk management aligned with ISO31000:2018 and GPMF standards, enables Babcock to mitigate potential risks and capitalise on opportunities ensuring the achievement of the project objectives. By adhering to these principles, Babcock demonstrates best practices in project management, driving successful outcomes in a dynamic and challenging environment.

Appendices

Appendix A: Different Methodologies

Appendix A: Methodologies advantages and disadvantages

Table 2: Methodology advantages and disadvantages.

Methodology	Advantages	Disadvantages
PRINCE2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ideal for linear projects. • Based on project management best practises. • Is a full project management methodology. • Can be used on any project type or size. • Principles can be applied universally. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Doesn't cover soft skills. • Requires senior management buy-in to be successful. • Requires experience to apply it well. • Can be documentation heavy. • Only supports waterfall approach.
Agile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More flexible. • Gets products to market faster. • Better communication. • Customer focused. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard to predict. • Final product isn't release first. • Documentation can get forgotten.
Six Sigma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhanced quality. • Process optimisation. • Data-driven decision making. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time-intensive. • Complex methodology.
APM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Iterative Process can be divided into short cycles or sprints, allowing for reassessment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Due to its iterative nature, can make it challenging to predict project timelines and outcomes accurately.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration: cooperation between team members and stakeholders, including frequent feedback loops. • Flexibility: Ability to adapt to changing requirements and priorities. • Continuous Improvement: Regular reflection and adjustment to improve processes and outcomes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous changes and additions can lead to scope creep, where new features and tasks are added, causing delays and resource strain. • High dependency on customer interaction. • Resource Management Issues. • Difficulty in Scaling. • Misunderstanding customer feedback can lead to incorrect development paths.
Project Management Institute (PMI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong control over project stages. • Effective for managing high-risk projects. • Supports clear cost analysis and budgeting. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less suitable for highly flexible or agile projects. • High-level project management structure may not fit smaller teams or experimental projects.

References

1. Agile Business Consortium (2014). DSDM Project Framework. [online] [www.agilebusiness.org](https://www.agilebusiness.org/dsdm-project-framework.html). Available at: <https://www.agilebusiness.org/dsdm-project-framework.html>. [Accessed 25 Nov. 2024].
2. APM (2010). Project Risk Analysis and Management guide. 2nd ed. High Wycombe England: Apm Pub.
3. APM (2015). Planning, scheduling, Monitoring and Control : the Practical Project Management of time, Cost and Risk. Princes Risborough, Buckinghamshire: Association for Project Management.
4. APM (2019). APM Body of Knowledge. 7th ed. Princes Risborough, Buckinghamshire: Association for Project Management.
5. APM (2022). APM Body of Knowledge. 7th ed. Princes Risborough, Buckinghamshire: Association for Project Management.
6. APM (2023). APM Project Management Qualification Study Guide. Princes Risborough, Buckinghamshire: Association For Project Management.
7. APM (2024a). APM Project Management Qualification Learner Study Pack. Princes Risborough, Buckinghamshire: Association for Project Management.
8. APM (2024b). What Is Scheduling in Project management? | APM. [online] [Apm.org.uk](https://www.apm.org.uk). Available at: <https://www.apm.org.uk/resources/what-is-project-management/what-is-scheduling-in-project-management/> [Accessed 31 Oct. 2024].
9. Association for Project Management (2016). Difference between agile and waterfall approaches | APM. [online] [Apm.org.uk](https://www.apm.org.uk). Available at: <https://www.apm.org.uk/resources/find-a-resource/agile-project-management/difference-between-agile-and-waterfall-approaches/>. [Accessed 5 Nov. 2024].
10. Association for Project Management (2017). Agile methods. [online] www.apm.org.uk. Available at: <https://www.apm.org.uk/resources/find-a-resource/agile-project-management/agile-methods/>. [Accessed 5 Nov. 2024].
11. Babcock International Group (2020). Governance. [online] Babcock International Group. Available at: <https://www.babcockinternational.com/sustainability/governance/> Updated 2024. [Accessed 15 Nov. 2024].

12. Babcock International Group (2023a). ESG policies and statements. [online] Babcock International. Available at: <https://www.babcockinternational.com/sustainability/esg-policies-and-statements/> Updated 2024. [Accessed 15 Nov. 2024].
13. Babcock International Group (2023b). Group Risk Management Policy. [online] Babcock International Group. Available at: <https://www.babcockinternational.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Group-Risk-Management-Policy.pdf> [Accessed 5 Nov. 2024].
14. Babcock International Group (2024). Anti-Bribery and Corruption/Ethical Policy. [online] Babcock International Group. Available at: <https://www.babcockinternational.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Anti-Bribery-and-Corruption-Ethical-Policy-.pdf>. [Accessed 5 Nov. 2024].
15. Buehring, S. (2023). PRINCE2 Benefits | Advantages and Disadvantages of PRINCE2 | Knowledge Train. [online] www.knowledgetrain.co.uk. Available at: <https://www.knowledgetrain.co.uk/project-management/prince2/prince2-course/prince2-benefits> [Accessed 17 Nov. 2024].
16. Chronicle (2024). Project Presentation Software Builds Microsoft Project Gantt Charts | OnePager Pro. [online] Onepager.com. Available at: https://www.onepager.com/howto/project_presentation_software.html [Accessed 24 Nov. 2024].
17. Financial Reporting Council (2024). UK Corporate Governance Code. [online] FRC (Financial Reporting Council). Available at: <https://www.frc.org.uk/library/standards-codes-policy/corporate-governance/uk-corporate-governance-code/>. [Accessed 5 Dec. 2024].
18. Hart, R. (2022). What Is Agile Methodology? Agile Methodologies Simplified. [online] management.org. Available at: <https://management.org/agile-methodology> [Accessed 5 Nov. 2024].
19. Hoban, S.M. (2022). What Is Project Scheduling? Your Guide to Better Project Timelines. [online] The Digital Project Manager. Available at: <https://thedigitalprojectmanager.com/projects/managing-schedules/what-is-project-scheduling/#how-to-schedule-projects-using-project-methodologies> [Accessed 4 Dec. 2024].

20. ILX Group (2017). PRINCE2 Processes - 7 Processes of PRINCE2 Explained | UK. [online] Prince2.com. Available at: <https://www.prince2.com/uk/prince2-processes> [Accessed 5 Nov. 2024].
21. ISO (2018). ISO 31000:2018 risk management — guidelines. [online] ISO. Available at: <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:31000:ed-2:v1:en> [Accessed 8 Nov. 2024].
22. Jovanovic, P. and Beric, I. (2018). Analysis of the Available Project Management Methodologies. *Management: Journal of Sustainable Business and Management Solutions in Emerging Economies*, 23(3), p.1.
23. Lawton, I. (2015). *Prince2 made simple*. Weymouth: P2ms Press.
24. Martins, N. (2022). The pros & cons of 8 project management methodologies. [online] Notion. Available at: <https://www.notion.so/blog/project-management-methodologies> [Accessed 15 Nov. 2024].
25. Masood, Z.A. (2017). The Benefits and Key Challenges of Agile Project Management under Recent Research Opportunities. [online] ResearchGate. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/316239082_The_Benefits_and_Key_Challenges_of_Agile_Project_Management_under_Recent_Research_Opportunities [Accessed 15 Nov. 2024].
26. Miller, D. (2020). Project Management Methodologies & Their Pros and Cons. [online] ProProfs Project Blog. Available at: <https://www.proprofsproject.com/blog/project-management-methodologies/> [Accessed 15 Nov. 2024].
27. Morphy, T. (2023). Project Methodologies versus Techniques and Tools. [online] Stakeholdermap.com. Available at: <https://www.stakeholdermap.com/project-management/project-methods-vs-tools-techniques.html> [Accessed 15 Nov. 2024].
28. Obergfell, Y. (2024). *Six Sigma Revealed Training Book Second Edition* by International Six Sigma Institute. [online] Available at: https://www.sixsigma-institute.org/contents/Six_Sigma_Revealed_by_International_Six_Sigma_Institute.pdf [Accessed 25 Nov. 2024].
29. PMI (2018). *The Agile Manifesto*. [online] Pmi.org. Available at: <https://www.pmi.org/disciplined-agile/agile/theagilemanifesto> [Accessed 25 Nov. 2024].

30. Projcon Admin (2019). Project Controls : What is it and why is it important ? [online] Projectcontrolsonline.com. Available at: <https://projectcontrolsonline.com/definition-and-importance-of-project-controls> [Accessed 31 Oct. 2024].
31. Quick, L. (2023). History of Agile Methodology: How it was developed. [online] www.knowledgehut.com. Available at: <https://www.knowledgehut.com/blog/agile/history-of-agile> [Accessed 6 Nov. 2024].
32. SCHEINER, M. (2022). Project Management Methodologies Comparison (11 PM Methods). [online] CRM.org. Available at: <https://crm.org/news/project-management-methodologies> [Accessed 6 Nov. 2024].
33. Scribbr (2019). What's the difference between method and methodology? [online] Scribbr. Available at: <https://www.scribbr.com/frequently-asked-questions/method-vs-methodology/> [Accessed 6 Nov. 2024].
34. Teamwork.com ed., (2023). Project Management Methodologies Examples & Overview | Teamwork.com. [online] Teamwork.com. Available at: <https://www.teamwork.com/project-management-guide/project-management-methodologies/#15-pmis-pmbok> [Accessed 17 Oct. 2024].
35. Westland, J. (2018). Six Sigma: A Simple Guide for Project Managers. [online] ProjectManager.com. Available at: <https://www.projectmanager.com/blog/six-sigma-a-simple-guide-for-project-managers> [Accessed 15 Nov. 2024].
36. Wikipedia (2019). Gantt chart. [online] Wikipedia. Available at: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gantt_chart [Accessed 31 Oct. 2024].
37. Wolcott, N. (2014). A Brief History of Time(lines): Henry Gantt and his Revolutionary Chart | OnePager Blog. [online] Onepager.com: A Brief History of Time(lines): Henry Gantt and his Revolutionary Chart. Available at: <https://www.onepager.com/community/blog/a-brief-history-of-the-gantt-chart/> [Accessed 31 Oct. 2024].